

**MANAGEMENT OF DIFFERENT CASES OF AVN THROUGH AYURVEDIC
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ABSTRACT

The spine is the main structure of support of human skeleton. It has flexibility due to elasticity of the spinal discs & ligaments. The average length of spinal cord in adult males is 71cm and in adult female is 60 cm. It supports the body weight of human and allows the body to move in all directions. It is made up of 7 cervical vertebrae, 12 thoracic vertebrae, 5 lumbar vertebrae, 5 sacral vertebrae and 4 coccyx vertebrae. In modern era; poor posture, a disorganised life style with bad food habits, corporate culture with smart phones and computers, prolonged posture associated with the spine leads spinal disorders such as lumbar spine stenosis, spondylitis & A.V.N (Avascular Necrosis). AVN is a bone disease characterized by necrosis of the bone due to loss of blood supply. The hip joint is the most common location for AVN to develop, although other joints may also be affected. Ayurvedic Neurotherapy is the preferred (recommended) treatment option for AVN in ancient practice. Ayurvedic Neurotherapy works on the nervous system; regenerating nerve, thereby achieves complete recovery from the symptoms of AVN. Ayurvedic Neurotherapy is a specialized and unique therapy offered as medicine for spine and joint disorder. Ayurvedic Neurotherapy can be successfully implemented to treat these conditions without surgical intervention. This article presented case reports of AVN successfully treated with Ayurvedic Neurotherapy.

KEYWORDS: Spine, Ayurvedic Neurotherapy, AVN, Avascular Necrosis.**INTRODUCTION**

Spinal disorders, or spinal defects, typically occur as a result of poor lifestyle, bad food habits, nutritional deficiency and age related degeneration. They are more common in women than men. AVN is such type of disease comes under the umbrella of spinal disorders. AVN is the disease of the bones, when the cells of the bone die due to reduced blood supply resulting in degeneration of nerves and deformity of bone. AVN can be correlated with *Asthi-Majjagata Vata* in Ayurveda since this disorder includes both edema and necrosis in the head of femur.

Causes of AVN

1. Excessive alcohol intake and tobacco smoking
2. Prolonged use of corticosteroids, steroidal medications
3. Elevated lipid deposition in blood

4. Arterial blockage
5. Legg-Calve-Perthes
6. Excessive nitrogen release into blood
7. HIV disease / S. L. E. (Systematic Lupus Erythematous-SLE)
8. Organ transplantation
9. Joint inflammation
10. Sickle Cell Anemia, other blood related disorders etc.
11. Traumatic injuries, etc.

Prevalence are more common in females than males, common age of onset is 30-60 years. Primarily affects the hip joint; may also affect the shoulder, wrist, ankle, and hand and foot joints. Symptoms may include pain around the affected joint, pain in the back that radiates to the knees, pain in the hip or buttock region, pain when attempting to put any weight on the hips, knees, or any

part of the lower body, inflammation of the hip joint, bone degeneration, arthritic and osteophyte production and stiffness in the hip and lower back.

Stages of AVN

Various stages of AVN are depicted in **Figure 1**, Stage-I is asymptomatic, identified by MRI. Stage-II involves

radiographic changes, sclerosis and osteopenia. Stage-III involves joint space narrowing, round contour compromised & movement declines. Stage IV involves collapse of subchondral bone.

Figure 1: Stages of AVN.

The standard treatment protocols in allopathic medicine recommend NSAIDs (Non Steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs) and steroid medications as a guideline for the management of AVN. Surgical interventions are also encouraged for AVN. Ayurveda proposes a different system of management of AVN under the title; Ayurvedic Neurotherapy (ANT). ANT is based on the change in anatomy and physiology of bone and joint structures. Ayurvedic Neurotherapy methodology consists of therapy and treatment over a period of days or habits as per time line.

Ayurvedic Neurotherapy

Ayurvedic Neurotherapy is an innovative therapy; it is a blessing for spine and joint disorders. Ayurvedic Neurotherapy can rectify the spine or joint disorders without any surgical approach. It has shown the results in patients of spine and joint disorders, including AVN who have lost all will and hope for being cured. Ayurvedic Neurotherapy involves various techniques like vacuum cupping, hot needling, leech therapy, *Agnikarma*, nerve massage and tractions & stem therapies, etc. This article presented case reports of AVN successfully treated with Ayurvedic Neurotherapy as mentioned below:

CASE REPORTS

Case – 1

A 30-year-old male from West Delhi, with a history of steroidal abuse, presented with pain in the buttocks and knees, along with difficulty in walking and sitting. Investigations including CBC, LFT, lipid profile, and MRI were performed. MRI findings revealed a damaged ball and Avascular Necrosis (AVN) of the left femoral head, classified as Stage II.

Case – 2

A 58-year-old male from Ajmer, complained of pain in the hip region radiating to the right leg and knee, along with difficulty in sitting and walking. Investigations such as CBC, X-ray, and MRI were conducted. Diagnosis confirmed AVN with oedematous head and neck (Stage II).

Case – 3

A 38-year-old male from Taleda, Bundi, reported pain while sitting and lying down, along with stiffness in the hip and knee joints and inflammation in the knee joint. CBC and MRI were performed, which confirmed AVN involving both femoral heads (Stage II).

Case – 4

A 28-year-old male from Baswada, Rajasthan, presented with pain in the left leg and difficulty walking, accompanied by sleeplessness due to continuous overnight pain. CBC and MRI investigations revealed AVN affecting both femoral heads (Stage III).

Case – 5

A 32-year-old male, complained of pain in the hip region, back, knee joints, and legs. Investigations including CBC and MRI were carried out, which showed AVN of the right femoral head with irregular thinning of the articular cortex and indistinct margins, corresponding to Stage I.

TREATMENT PROTOCOL

The patient underwent Ayurvedic Neurotherapy for duration of seven days, in combination with internal medicinal treatment. The following medications were administered.

✓ Nerobhi Plus Capsule – 1 capsule twice daily.

- ✓ Nerobhi Plus Oil – for local massage.
- ✓ AO3 Oil – applied externally at night.
- ✓ *Ashwagandha Churna* – taken with milk.
- ✓ Nerobhilax Powder – taken with lukewarm water.

Ayurvedic Neurotherapy Procedural Protocol

The patient's clothes were removed, and they were positioned comfortably on the therapy table.

1. **Abhyanga:** A gentle massage was performed using oil, focusing particularly on the hands and feet, with special emphasis on the soles to stimulate circulation.
2. **Jwala Dhvani Yantra Vidhi:** Hot cupping using flame-generated vacuum (*Ghati Yantra*) was applied over the hip region, thighs, legs, and feet to enhance blood flow and relieve stiffness.
3. **Vacuum Cupping:** Vacuum cups were applied over the affected lower limb regions for about 5–10 minutes to improve local perfusion and remove stagnated toxins.

After completion, the patient was wiped cleaned with a dry cloth and then placed in the prone position. The entire sequence of therapy was repeated to ensure uniform stimulation and improved therapeutic outcomes.

The next step, performed by the doctor, involved gentle cervical and lumbar therapies with a primary focus on AVN therapy. Fixation of protruded hip joints, sacroiliac joints (S1, S2), and inwardly displaced tailbone was carried out using the punch technique along with *Bhujangasana*, repeated 3–4 times until proper alignment was achieved. The key AVN points—MA1, MA2, and

MA3—located around the iliofemoral ligament were stimulated; MA1 and MA2 were worked on in a half-butterfly posture to relieve stiffness, improve muscle flexibility, and restore blood circulation, while pressure on MA3 (between the pelvis and genital area) helped open restricted hip joints, reduce pain, and promote bone regeneration. Light traction was applied to the hip, thigh, and leg 3–4 times to relieve pain, open joint spaces, and improve the range of motion. Hot Needling (*Viddha Karma*) was then performed by inserting and heating acupuncture needles at pain sites to reduce pain and inflammation. *Jalaukavacharan* was applied once weekly to eliminate toxins and reduce inflammation, followed by *Sukshma Agnikarma* using a red-hot *Shalaka* on pain points, with aloe vera rubbed afterward for soothing. Nerve massage was performed using thumb tips, and *Basti* was administered locally over affected areas. *Nadi Swedan* was given to reduce pain and inflammation.

Dietary Protocol

Pathya: Raw food, Juicy fruit, Milk, Dry fruits, Sprouts, Alkaline Diet, etc.

Apathya: Junk food, spicy, oily, fried and sour foods, etc.

RESULT AND OBSERVATIONS

The prescribed therapy observed significant improvement in assessment parameters and MRI imaging as depicted in **Table 1** and **Table 2** respectively. **Figure 2**, depicted comparative improvement in disease parameters after the therapy.

Table 1: Assessment Scale (Before and After Therapy).

Parameters	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
Range of Motion (ROM)	Restricted	Restricted	Restricted	Restricted	Restricted
After Therapy (ROM)	Free flexion, extension, rotation				
Pain Scale (Before)	4	4	4	5	4
Pain Scale (After)	2	1	2	3	0
Stiffness (Before)	+	+	+	+	+
Stiffness (After)	–	–	–	–	–
Inflammation (Before)	+	+	+	+	+
Inflammation (After)	–	–	–	–	–
Stage of AVN (Before)	II	II	II	III	III
Stage of AVN (After)	I	I	I	II	II
Difficulty in Walking (Before)	+	+	+	+	+
Difficulty in Walking (After)	–	–	–	–	–
Difficulty in Sitting (Before)	+	+	+	+	+
Difficulty in Sitting (After)	–	–	–	–	–
Limping (Before)	+	+	+	+	+
Limping (After)	–	–	–	–	–

Table 2: Improvement in MRI/Imaging parameters.

MRI Results in Cases	Before Treatment	After Treatment (3 months after)
Case-1	Damaged ball, edema in left head of femur Stage-2 AVN	Reduced Ball damage, no signs of edema in left femoral head Stage-1 AVN
Case-2	Edema in head and neck of right femur Stage-2 AVN	Absent Stage-1 AVN
Case-3	AVN, bilateral femoral head necrosis Stage-2 AVN	Absent in right head of femur Stage-1 AVN
Case-4	AVN- both sides of Femoral head Stage-3 AVN	Signs of necrosis in right head of femur Stage-1 AVN
Case-5	AVN of head of right head of femur, irregular articular cortex of femoral head with margins Stage-2 AVN	Edema in head of right femur Stage-1 AVN

Figure 2: Comparative improvement in disease parameters after the therapy.**DISCUSSION**

AVN (Avascular Necrosis) is a health crisis due to modern era lifestyle. Ayurvedic Neuro therapy comprises of a unique technique which deals with holistic treatment of AVN. It includes daily practice of therapy treatment on painful local areas two times a day for minimum of 7 days along with oral medicines and dietary protocols. The therapy include Ayurvedic procedures like *Abhyanga* with *Sarson* oil, Hot cupping, Vacuum cupping, Hot needling, Leech therapy, *Agnikarma* and nerve massage, etc. indicated according to patient profile. The oral medicines prescribed along with therapies also played an important role in spine, nerve & muscle health. These therapies act significantly in increasing blood flow, relief pain, reduces inflammation by decreasing cytokine receptor strength and reduced stiffness thus improved overall spine health.

CONCLUSION

The results of Ayurvedic Neurotherapy (ANT) for individuals with Avascular Necrosis (AVN) were very promising. All five subjects had significant pain relief, and acutely, the swelling around the hip joints and knees were reduced. Gradually, the AVN grade decreased without surgery. The patients were able to ambulate and sit without pain and perform activities of daily living after therapy. Additionally, MRI reports demonstrated clear improvement after three months, supporting the efficacy of ANT to treat AVN.

Thus it can be stated that Ayurvedic Neuro therapy is the therapy which cures AVN from its root and gives anatomical and physiological results without any surgeries. Ayurvedic Neuro Therapy has been proven to be a blessing for all patients who were suffering from AVN or any other spine and joint disorders. Ayurvedic

Neurotherapy is the only therapy which can reverse MRI results without any adverse effect.

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